

CRACoWi

Cybersecurity Compliance Made Easy

CRACoWi at a Glance

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Authors:
A. Papagiannaki, K. Agavanakis

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Introduction

The digitalization of global economy drives new consumer and business behaviors, which demand increasingly intelligent solutions, and will end up to an ecosystem consisting of billions of intelligent systems and millions of applications, where interconnected devices and services collect, exchange and process data in order to adapt dynamically to their context. As such, Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) play an increasingly important role in the socio-economic activities and in the Critical Infrastructure (CI), i.e. the systems and assets, whether physical or virtual (e.g. water, energy, transport, communications, health and financial services), so vital to a city or country that their incapacity or destruction would have a debilitating impact on the national security, economy, health or safety [1].

In this emerging landscape, the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) has introduced a globally recognized standard for cybersecurity in the Internet of Things (IoT). The TS 103645 standard lays the foundation for future IoT certification schemes and defines a security framework for IoT devices [2]. The standard highlights the growing importance of IoT cybersecurity, noting that as more devices get connected to the internet, the cybersecurity of the Internet of Things (IoT) is becoming a growing concern, as "People entrust their personal data to an increasing number of online devices and services."

In parallel, European Union bodies (e.g. ENISA) have consistently raised concerns about the cybersecurity risks posed by insecure computing systems, connected devices and embedded systems, with a special concern for IoT devices (due to their resources-constrained nature), particularly in critical infrastructures and Smart City applications, to help manufacturers and consumers make informed decisions within the European Network & Information Security (NIS) threat landscape evolution [3][4][5]. These vulnerabilities threaten sensitive data, public safety, essential resources like electricity and water, and asset-dependent services such as smart metering, e-mobility and financial services.

In October 2024 the EU adopted the Cyber Resilience Act (CRA) [6], to address such challenges by establishing mandatory cybersecurity requirements for hardware and software products sold within the EU. The CRA reflects the EU's commitment to fostering a safer and more secure digital environment, aiming to enhance consumer protection, secure digital infrastructure, and strengthen the bloc's technological resilience through a chain of trust that involves all the stakeholders in the entire products' life-cycle.

CRACoWi

Aligned with the European Union's strategic objectives, the CRACoWi project is a forward-looking initiative designed to meet the growing cybersecurity demands of the evolving digital landscape [7]. At its core, lies the "Cyber Resilience Act - Compliance Wizard," an innovative digital assistant (wizard) that delivers a comprehensive suite of methodologies, processes, and tools to help a diverse range of stakeholders to ensure cybersecurity across the entire product supply chain, empower SMEs—including manufacturers, distributors, and importers—in meeting the stringent requirements of the EU's Cyber Resilience Act (CRA).

Leveraging artificial intelligence, the Compliance Wizard ensures efficient self-assessment, supports cybersecurity certifications, and fosters an environment of harmonized cybersecurity practices for product security and continuous improvement throughout its entire life cycle, from design phase to end-of-life, including key components as:

- **Automated Compliance Assessments**, to simplify adherence to CRA requirements through AI-driven self-assessment tools.
- **Documentation Support**, to generate the necessary regulatory documents to streamline certification processes.
- **Enhanced Product Security**, to integrate robust security features directly into the product lifecycle.

The comprehensive lifecycle approach includes the provision of advanced automated tools, methodology for actionable insights, and guidelines for capacity-building resources with the aim to strengthen protection, address vulnerabilities, and counter cyber threat. Addressing both immediate compliance needs and long-term resilience, CRACoWi promotes cross-sector partnerships and knowledge exchange.

Manufacturers, regulatory bodies and supply chain stakeholders are represented by the 14 project consortium partners from 4 countries (Greece, Germany, Slovenia, and Cyprus), in a collaborative effort that combines diverse - yet complementary - expertise across the value chain

Collaborative Efforts

A business proposal is aimed at attracting potential clients with what a company sells. It's a document in either digital or printed form that explains product or service features, taking into consideration the lead's needs and wants. In other words, business proposals show how a company can help solve a customer's specific problem.

Industry Leaders

Enhancing global cybersecurity practices and regulatory alignment.

- **7LAYERS (BUREAU VERITAS)**, offering extensive testing, certification, and cybersecurity standards expertise.
- **MOTOR OIL (Hellas)**, contributing expertise in cybersecurity, energy technology, and regulatory alignment.

Innovative SMEs

Driving technological advancements in IoT security, AI, and compliance automation.

- **ITML**, specializing in IT integration, data management, and telecommunications services tailored to the EU public sector.
- **ONEKEY**, providing advanced IoT security platforms capable of vulnerability detection without source code access, coupled with AI-powered compliance tools.
- **SLOA**, offering big data, AI, and management consulting expertise to enhance IoT compliance testing.
- **APPART**, integrated software solutions for the Telecommunications, Energy, Banking, and Health sectors
- **ERMINAS**, specializing in B2B software solutions in the areas of enterprise applications and Industrial IoT
- **SEVENSHIFT**, delivering cutting-edge software, data analytics, and cybersecurity assessments through platforms like Bunkai.
- **MEAZON**, a leader in energy digitization and Low Voltage power grid optimization through a holistic cyber-physical approach that leverages IoT, ML and digital twin technologies.

IndustrNational Authorities and Research Hubs

Ensuring alignment with EU-wide cybersecurity strategies and standards.

- The Greek Centre for Technological Support, Development and Innovation (KETYAK), reinforcing public sector cybersecurity initiatives with essential tools and processes.
- The Slovenian Digital Innovation Hub (DIHS), supporting digital transformation and cybersecurity among SMEs.
- The Government Information Security Office of the Republic of Slovenia, acting as a national authority on information security, aligning CRACoWi with EU cybersecurity strategies.

Specialized Partners

- MOTOR OIL RENEWABLE ENERGY (affiliated with MOTOR OIL), focusing on clean energy solutions that integrate advanced cybersecurity principles.
- Centre for Technological Support, Development & Innovation, bringing technical expertise in digital transformation.

EU Project Dissemination

- Tiko Pro, ensuring effective outreach and dissemination of project results to maximize impact across EU member states.

Objectives & Strategic Impact

Devoted to address critical cybersecurity challenges, CRACoWi combines expertise in cybersecurity, IoT, and digital transformation to advance European Union's cybersecurity framework across diverse sectors, including critical infrastructure, energy systems, and IoT ecosystems. It targets gaps in product security by addressing vulnerabilities, ensuring consistent security updates, and improving user awareness. The project's lifecycle-based approach prioritizes proactive measures to tackle cybersecurity costs and risks in products containing digital components. These challenges are underscored by the staggering economic impact of global cyberattacks, which were estimated to cost EUR 5.5 trillion in 2021.

COMPLIANCE ■ **RESILIENCE**
TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATION

CRACoWi addresses key challenges (compliance, resilience, and technological innovation) through a holistic approach and empowers stakeholders to demonstrate compliance to regulatory authorities while effectively communicating their cybersecurity posture to international markets. This way, it delivers scalable and impactful solutions totally aligned with EU regulations and strategies, that strengthen the cybersecurity posture of European SMEs and safeguard economic activity and sustainable growth in a more secure and resilient digital ecosystem.

The initiative's solutions aim to mitigate Inadequate Security Measures (reducing pervasive vulnerabilities and strengthening update practices), and Limited User Awareness (Promoting adoption of secure products through education and capacity-building efforts). This is achieved through:

- **Regulatory Alignment:** Seamless integration with the EU Cyber Resilience Act (CRA) and existing certification frameworks.
- **Lifecycle Security Management:** Addressing security needs from product design to end-of-life, ensuring continuous monitoring of vulnerabilities.
- **Technical and Strategic Outreach:** Combining advanced tools with dissemination efforts to equip stakeholders with the knowledge and skills needed to navigate complex cybersecurity regulations.

By integrating technical solutions with certification standards and capacity-building initiatives, CRACoWi offers a comprehensive framework that enhances compliance and resilience. The project promotes a unified perspective that spans the product lifecycle, proactively identifies emerging vulnerabilities, and ensures scalability across sectors and borders. In doing so, CRACoWi contributes to creating a safer, more resilient digital environment that aligns with the EU's vision for cybersecurity excellence.

Project components

To facilitate the adoption of the EU Cyber Resilience Act (CRA) among SMEs, the CRACoWi project is developing innovative platform where "Cyber Resilience Act Compliance - Wizard" (CRACoWi) stands as its core element. It offers a comprehensive cybersecurity framework, integrating cutting-edge security-by-design principles to streamline CRA compliance processes. The solution ensures that cybersecurity is embedded from a product's inception and sustained throughout its lifecycle. Additionally, the CRACoWi platform prepares manufacturers to meet future certification requirements, equipping them to address emerging cybersecurity threats effectively.

Key Features of the CRACoWi Platform

The CRACoWi platform comprises several advanced components designed to simplify and enhance the CRA compliance process:

Automated Test Cases

These features validate critical security requirements using firmware data, enabling manufacturers to assess their product's cybersecurity posture with minimal effort.

Interactive Self-Assessment

Guided by AI-powered tools, including large language models, the platform provides a step-by-step evaluation process aligned with CRA standards.

Automated Documentation Creation

Utilizing artificial intelligence, the platform processes existing product and procedural documentation to generate essential compliance artifacts, such as statements of conformity and technical documents.

Implementation and Use Cases

The CRACoWi project will implement and validate its technology across a diverse set of use cases, demonstrating its broad applicability and versatility in meeting the CRA's requirements. These use cases span multiple industries, applications, and product categories, showcasing the platform's ability to address specific compliance challenges.

1. Secure Software Development

ERMINAS will lead two use cases focused on integrating security measures into SME software development. These use cases include tools for managing library security and ensuring compliance for industrial software deployments. ERMINAS will also target secure development of CRA-compliant cloud applications, specifically Class I critical software for web and mobile applications tailored to critical infrastructure needs.

2. Energy Sensor Compliance

MEAZON, an energy sensor manufacturer, will use the CRA Compliance Wizard to align its advanced metering and energy sensors with CRA standards. These devices, integral to smart city applications and critical infrastructure management, incorporate technologies like 5G, Zigbee, and WiFi.

3. Electrical Substation Devices

The Independent Power Transmission Operator, along with APAPRT and MORE, will identify vulnerabilities in Class I electrical substation devices. This use case leverages vulnerability management tools and industry-specific testing environments.

4. Importer and Distributor Compliance

ITML will focus on ensuring CRA compliance for critical infrastructure components managed by importers and distributors, verifying standards throughout the product lifecycle.

5. Device Certification

Bureau Veritas will certify Class II devices using the Compliance Wizard, ensuring they meet CRA cybersecurity standards before market entry.

6. Supply Chain Risk Management

MOTOROIL and ITML will explore how the Wizard supports supply chain risk management by accelerating cybersecurity assessments for critical safety and security devices.

**Demonstrating
CRACoWi's
capabilities and
testing the limits of
the Compliance
Wizard in specialized
situations**

Conclusion

CRACoWi aims to create a transparent and standardized approach to cybersecurity, embedding robust security principles throughout product development and lifecycle management. This unified approach not only enhances the digital resilience of SMEs but also streamlines regulatory compliance and fortifies Europe's overall cybersecurity governance. By leveraging advanced tools, efficient processes, and a collaborative framework, CRACoWi showcases its adaptability and innovation in addressing diverse cybersecurity challenges across industries.

The project proactively identifies emerging vulnerabilities, enabling stakeholders to respond effectively, while ensuring scalability and applicability across sectors and borders. Through its comprehensive strategy, CRACoWi aligns with the EU's vision for cybersecurity excellence, while the actual impact of this holistic approach in cybersecurity governance extends beyond regulatory alignment to socio-economic resilience and stability reinforcement in the digital and economic landscape of Europe.

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